

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds—Part XXVI. Synthesis and Screening of New 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-Substituted *p*-Sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles

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A number of 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles have been synthesised by the condensation of fifteen different 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and benzoylhydrazine and the products screened by cup-plate agar diffusion method against three micro-organisms *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* for their antibacterial activity.

IN a phased programme on the study of structure-activity relationship of 3, 5-diaryl-4-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles¹⁻⁵, we here report the synthesis of some new azoles of the type I having the nitro and ethoxyl groups in the phenyl rings attached at positions 3 and 5 respectively of the azole nucleus with a view to study the effect of these substituents on the antibacterial properties and compare these results with those obtained earlier with the azoles having the methoxyl, or alkyl groups in the phenyl ring at position-5.

These were synthesised by condensing 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine and benzoylhydrazine under different reaction conditions. The homogeneity and purity of all these products was confirmed by TLC and structure assigned on the basis of analogous work reported earlier⁷.

Azoles of all the three series were later subjected to *in vitro* screening against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* at two different concentrations of 500 ug/ml and 250 ug/ml and the results obtained with lower concentration are recorded in Tables 1 to 3.

Experimental

The intermediates 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl) propane-1, 3-dione and its azo derivatives required for this work were prepared by employing the method already reported earlier⁶.

TABLE 1.—3-(*p*-NITROPHENYL)-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES
(Fig. 1 : R₁ = H)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisa- tion solvent	Molecular formula	Percentage				Antibacterial Properties		
							Found C	H	Requires C	H	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyo- cyanea</i>
1.	H	291-2	YO	85	GAA/DMF	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	56.0	4.3	56.1	4.1	(-)	(+)	(+++)
2.	Acetyl	285-6	YO	86	GAA/DMF	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ S	56.3	4.0	56.2	4.1	(-)	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	292	O	75	GAA	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	61.5	4.3	61.8	4.2	(-)	(+)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	227	RF	80	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	62.0	4.4	61.9	4.4	(-)	(+)	(+++)
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	242	RF	79	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	62.1	4.5	61.9	4.4	(-)	(-)	(++)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	233	YB	82	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	61.7	4.3	61.9	4.4	(-)	(-)	(+)
7.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	234	OSF	78	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	57.9	4.0	57.8	3.8	(-)	(+)	(+++)
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	235	SRF	73	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	57.9	4.0	57.8	3.8	(-)	(-)	(+++)
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	265	O	83	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	57.8	3.9	57.8	3.8	(-)	(-)	(-)
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	280	YO	85	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	53.7	3.6	53.8	3.6	(-)	(-)	(-)
11.	Guanidyl	282-3	YO	70	GAA	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	54.0	4.1	53.9	4.0	(-)	(+)	(++)
12.	α -Pyridyl	290-1	SR	75	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ S	59.0	4.0	59.1	4.1	(-)	(-)	(-)
13.	2-Pyrimidinyl	>300	R	81	DMF	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	58.9	4.1	58.9	4.0	(-)	(++)	(-)
14.	2, 6-D.methyl-4- pyrimidinyl	282-3	YO	72	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	58.1	4.4	58.2	4.3	(+)	(+)	(-)
15.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4- thiadiazol-2-yl	290-1	SO	74	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	52.8	3.9	52.9	3.7	(-)	(+)	(-)

TABLE 2
1-PHENYL-3-(*p*-NITROPHENYL)-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES
(Fig. 1 : R₁ = C₆H₅)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisa- tion solvent	Molecular formula	Percentage				Antibacterial Activity		
							Found		Requires		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
							C	H	C	H			
1.	H	205	O	71	EtOH/GAA	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	61.3	4.1	61.3	4.2	(-)	(+)	(+++)
2.	Acetyl	205	O	69	EtOH/GAA	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆ S	61.3	4.2	61.0	4.3	(-)	(-)	(+++)
3.	Phenyl	155	OSN	78	EtOH/GAA	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.1	4.5	65.2	4.4	(+)	(+)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	237	RSN	70	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.9	4.4	65.7	4.6	(-)	(-)	(++)
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	194	RON	70	EtOH/GAA	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.8	4.9	65.7	4.6	(-)	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	237	RSN	71	EtOH/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	65.8	4.4	65.7	4.6	(+)	(+)	(+++)
7.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	238	ON	73	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₆ ClS	62.0	4.0	61.9	4.0	(-)	(++)	(+)
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	236	OS	70	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₆ ClS	61.8	4.1	61.9	4.0	(-)	(-)	(-)
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	232	R	75	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₆ ClS	61.9	4.0	61.9	4.0	(-)	(-)	(+)
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	245	R	77	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₆ BrS	58.0	3.9	58.1	3.7	(-)	(+)	(+)
11.	Guanidyl	290-1	YO	72	GAA/DMF	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	59.1	4.5	59.0	4.3	(-)	(+)	(+)
12.	α -Pyridyl	263	R	76	DMF	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₇ S	63.2	4.0	63.3	4.2	(-)	(-)	(-)
13.	2-Pyrimidinyl	>300	O	75	DMF	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₆ S	61.5	4.1	61.3	4.0	(-)	(-)	(++)
14.	4, 6-Dimethyl- 2-pyrimidinyl	279-80	OS	74	GAA	C ₃₅ H ₃₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	62.3	4.6	62.3	4.5	(-)	(+)	(+)
15.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-> thiadiazol-2-yl	300	O	69	GAA/DMF	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	58.0	4.0	57.7	3.9	(-)	(+)	(++)

TABLE 3.—1-BENZOYL-3-(*p*-NITROPHENYL)-5-(*p*-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL-
BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(Fig. 1 : R₁ = C₆H₅CO)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisa- tion solvent	Molecular formula	Percentage				Antibacterial Activity		
							Found		Requires		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyo- cyanea</i>
							C	H	C	H			
1.	H	283-4	YO	72	GAA/DMF	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₆ S	60.4	4.2	60.4	4.0	(-)	(-)	(+++)
2.	Acetyl	284	Y	71	GAA/DMF	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₆ S	60.3	4.1	60.2	4.1	(+)	(+)	(++++)
3.	Phenyl	229	R	74	EtOH/GAA	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₆ S	64.2	4.0	64.3	4.2	(+)	(+)	(+++)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	226	R	70	GAA/DMF	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆ S	64.7	4.0	64.7	4.4	(-)	(+)	(+++)
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	240	R	71	GAA/DMF	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆ S	64.6	4.4	64.7	4.4	(-)	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	232	YR	71	GAA/DMF	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆ S	64.9	4.5	64.7	4.4	(-)	(-)	(-)
7.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	229	R	73	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₆ ClS	61.0	4.0	61.1	3.8	(-)	(-)	(+)
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	230	RF	70	GAA/DMF	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₆ ClS	61.2	3.8	61.1	3.8	(-)	(-)	(-)
9.	Guanidyl	276	B	68	GAA/DMF	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₆ S	58.4	4.0	58.3	4.1	(-)	(-)	(-)
10.	α -Pyridyl	278	R	75	GAA/DMF	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₇ S	62.4	4.1	62.4	4.0	(-)	(+)	(++++)
11.	2-Pyrimidinyl	>300	R	72	GAA/DMF	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₆ S	60.4	4.0	60.5	3.9	(-)	(+)	(+)
12.	2, 6-Dimethyl-4- pyrimidinyl	280	O	73	GAA/DMF	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₆ S	61.5	4.4	61.5	4.3	(-)	(+)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4- thiadiazol-2-yl	297-8	OR	73	GAA/DMF	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₆ S ₂	57.1	3.7	57.1	3.7	(+)	(+)	(++)

GAA = Glacial acetic acid ; DMF = Dimethyl formamide ;

B = Brown ; F = Flakes ; N = Needles ; O = Orange ; R = Red ; S = Shining ; Y = Yellow.

Synthesis of 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazole :

To a solution of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-dione (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml), hydrazine hydrate (100% ; 0.05 g) was added and the contents refluxed in an oil bath at 160-70° for 5-6 hr. On keeping the contents overnight, an orange solid separated out, which was filtered, washed with water, dried and had m.p. 285°.

Pure 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazole was crystallised from glacial acetic acid-DMF mixture as a yellowish orange solid, m.p. 291-2° (Yield : 85%).

(Found : C, 56.0 ; H, 4.3. C₂₃H₂₀O₆N₆S requires C, 56.1 ; H, 4.1%).

Synthesis of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-phenyl *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazole

Phenylhydrazine (0.05 g) was added to a solution of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(*N*-phenyl *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-dione (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml)-ethanol (3 ml) mixture, the contents refluxed in a water bath for 6-7 hr and then left overnight. The separated solid was filtered, dried and had m.p. 148° ; pure 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-4-(*N*-phenyl *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazole was crystallised from ethanol-glacial acetic acid mixture in shining orange needles and had m.p. 155°. (Yield : 73%).

(Found : C, 65.1 ; H, 4.5. C₃₅H₂₈O₆N₆S requires C, 65.2 ; H, 4.4%).

The cyclisation reactions with benzoylhydrazine were similarly carried out but here the presence of

one or two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were found necessary.

Other compounds of all the three series were similarly prepared and have been recorded in Tables 1 to 3.

Antibacterial Activity :

These compounds were later subjected to *in vitro* screening against three micro-organisms *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* by cup-plate agar diffusion method at two different concentrations 500 ug/ml and 250 ug/ml and the results with the latter are entered in the Tables 1 to 3.

The results of antibacterial properties indicated that the activity against *P. pyocyanea* was of very high order as compared to that against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. On comparing the results with those obtained from 1-simple/substituted-3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-ethylphenyl)-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles⁵, it was clear that the replacement of an ethyl group in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 of pyrazole nucleus by an ethoxyl group decreased the activity of the compounds. It was also observed that shifting of nitro group from meta⁸ to the para position in the phenyl ring attached at position-3 of the pyrazole nucleus, increased the activity. Further, replacement of the hydrogen at position-1 of the pyrazole nucleus by a

benzoyl group increased the activity of the compounds against *S. aureus* and *P. pyocyanea*. When these results were compared with those obtained from 1-simple/substituted-3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles¹, it became evident that the replacement of the methoxyl by an ethoxyl group at para position of the phenyl ring the latter attached to position-5 of the pyrazole nucleus, decreased the activity of the compounds.

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